

MULICHE SHIKSHAN PRAGATICH LAKSHAN

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Still in certain parts of India a female child is considered as a burden this is where the cycle of neglect starts. India's obsession with bearing a male child aka "a heir" has led to heinous crimes against female gender such as Dowry deaths, Female Infanticide, Female Foeticide etc

The Indian government to rectify these disparities and to spread awareness among the masses have taken steps to educate, empower and encourage a girl child. Prime Minister Erna Solberg Of Norway quotes, "When you invest in a girl's education, she feeds herself, her children, her community & her nation. This quote emphasises the importance of female education for which many Schemes and Policies have been introduced by the Central and the State Government that are targeted to bring about Socio economic development of a girl child and adolescent women. Some of the schemes of the government are as follows:

- a) Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao*
- b) Sukanya Samridhi Yojna*
- c) CBSE Scholarship Scheme*
- d) Right to Education*
- e) Mukhyamantri Laadli Yojna – Uttar Pradesh*
- f) Mukhyamantri Kanya Suraksha Yojna - Bihar*
- g) Ladli scheme – Haryana*
- h) Kishori Shakti Yojana – Odisha*
- i) Saraswati Bicycle Scheme - Chhattisgarh.*

Keyword: *Disparities, Girl's education, educate, empower, encourage, Central, State Government, Schemes, Scholarships and Policies*

Introduction

As per the constitution of India, education is a fundamental right of every child, irrespective of that in many parts of India girls either drop out of school or are not allowed due to many factors which may include financial problems, family pressure, customs and traditions etc.

The Indian government both at the central and state level have taken efforts to promote education which includes free education till 8 grade and many schemes which aid higher studies. To understand the obstacles in the process of the girl's education a questionnaire was prepared and the sample students were encouraged to give responses. The sample students were girls of XII grade, who soon have to make major career decisions which might alter if they don't get necessary financial support.

This survey aims at highlighting the various government and non-government scholarships and suggestions

Analysis of the Data:

For this research purpose, female students belonging to different age groups were chosen (15-18). A total no. Of 65 students took part in the survey.

Opportunities, challenges and suggestions for improving girl's education

In India the Graduation system is classified into two parts: Under graduation (UG) and Postgraduation (PG). The undergraduate is for three years which are in the field arts, commerce, science apart from this there are many courses which along with graduation can be completed for e.g. C. A, C.S, diploma courses, Certified Financial Planner etc.

The sample consists of 65 female students of Jr College, that were on the verge of completing their higher secondary course, this is the period where one is supposed to take major career decisions like which college to choose from which diploma to go for, and the crucial one is whether I can afford this course, Degree college and Diplomas cost way more than they used to in this case 95% sample students considered pursuing higher Education, 47% of students preferred B.com as the cheapest course available. 35 % of the sample had considered dropping out of higher secondary due to non-availability of funds, which can be prevented if an effective counselling is provided to the girls. Almost every course has an option of scholarship either of which is provided by the state or central government, NGO or the new kick starter campaign along with this India is the first country in the world to make corporate social responsibility (CSR) mandatory, following an amendment to the Companies Act, 2013 in April 2014. Businesses can invest their profits in areas such as education, poverty, gender equality, and hunger as part of any CSR compliance. The amendment notified in the Companies Act, 2013 requires companies with a net worth of INR 500 crore or more, or an annual turnover of INR 1000 crore or more, or net profit of INR 5 crore or more, to spend 2 percent of their average net profits of three years on CSR. Irrespective of such schemes the sample were unaware of such aid.

Are you aware of the various scholarships and Educational schemes provided by the Indian Government

ARE YOU PLANNING TO PURSUE HIGHER STUDIES

Major Schemes by the Government and Non-government

1. Mazi Kanya Bhagyashree Scheme (MKBS) In 2016, the government of Maharashtra started a new scheme to replace the old Sukanya scheme called Mazi Kanya Bhagyashree scheme. Under this scheme, the economically weaker group or BPL category families are given financial assistance by the state government for survival and education of daughters.
2. PRAGATI SCHOLARSHIP Scholarship/Contingency is awarded to meritorious girls taking admission in AICTE approved Technical institution at Degree/ Diploma. Total 4000 scholarship are given @ Rs. 30000/- as tuition fee reimbursement and Rs. 20000/- as incidentals each year.

3. E-pathshala

CENTER SECTOR SCHOLARSHIP SCHEME FOR 12TH PASS SCIENCE, ARTS AND COMMERCE STUDENTS

Purpose – A total of 84000 scholarships will be provided to 50% of the girls as well as boys respectively. Award – 10,000 rupees will be offered per annum for about 3 years particularly for the graduation course and for the masters course it is 20,000 rupees per annum for two years.

4. G.P. BIRLA SCHOLARSHIP: This scholarship is granted mainly on courses like Science, Engineering, Humanities, Medicine, Commerce and Architecture.

Eligibility – The students should secure 80% marks in the state board or 85% marks in the central board.

Award – 50,000 rupees will be granted per annum.

- FAEA SCHOLARSHIP Purpose – The main purpose is to provide scholarship to students who basically belongs to the socially as well as economically disadvantaged parts of society. It gives the underprivileged students an opportunity for studying in various institutes that provides economic opportunity as well as academic excellence.

Award –Financial aid and support for completing higher education.

Challenges for Higher Education

- 1) Traditions, Customs, beliefs and practices: 21.67% of sample students expressed that there’s a possibility that they would be allowed to complete their graduation because of the pressure of getting married, if a girl is highly educated, she might not a get a good alliance due to certain stereotypes.15 % of the students expressed that the Family is not ready to support higher education as they feel girls have to help out with domestic chores
- 2) Tuitions: 13.33% of students expressed they might retain the course or find it challenging as they don’t have access to tutors
- 3) Finance: 76.67% of sample students responded that their family were supporting their decisions of pursuing higher studies but they didn’t have access to financial help which would either lead to dropping out of college or pursuing only B.com or alternate options like beauty courses or doing part time jobs
- 4) 32% of the students expressed if they had an access to financial help they would have opted for science.

Suggestions

- 1)Women teacher understands the problem of the female students hence appointing more female teachers
- 2)Appointment of qualified and trained teachers
- 3)Providing tools for conducting carrier aptitude test
- 4)Conducting sessions like career Mela where experts from the field can suggest and inform the requirements and eligibility in 9 std and 11 std
- 5)Providing PDF with access to links for various scholarship programme.

- 6) Providing free or concessional for tutoring
- 7) Counselling for parents
- 8) Providing a safe environment for both girls and boys
- 9) Explaining the eligibility and the process to avail scholarship
- 10) providing the lists of CSR financial aids and the process to avail the aid

WHAT SUPPORT SYSTEM YOU MAY NEED TO ACHIEVE YOUR DREAMS?

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CONCLUSION

When you educate a girl, you kick-start a cycle of success. It makes economic sense. It makes social sense. It makes moral sense." - Queen Rania of Jordan Scholarship provides a student channel through which they can source money so as to fund their educational needs, in the absence of such schemes and scholarship a student will have to either take a part time job or an educational loan bought of which puts the student in tremendous pressure to repay the debt and manage they hectic schedule of work and college hours.

Therefore, it's important to understand the selection process and eligibility of such scholarship and the impact of it on the girl's education. Its rightly emphasised that an Educated girl will grow up to be educated women, who in turn will participate in the nation's economy raise educated children, by educating girls we are not only developing our present but our future economy as well. Educated girls will be economically independent, in today's economy she can partake family responsibility, education will bring awareness with respect to her health, hygiene, family planning etc

But the most crucial of all education will give her strength to choose a career, to endeavour different opportunities to say no to abuse to walk out of difficult situations or marriage to live a life with dignity and honour. We need to realise a fact that no part of the society can prosper if an entire part of the society is marginalised and hence to build our nation, we have to build program that will help girls' education.

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